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A Retrospective Analysis Of Medication Errors Among Type-II Diabetes Diagnosed Patients With Hypertension In DHQ Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Background:

A significant public health concern nowadays is the rise in diabetes worldwide, especially in low-income nations. The intricacy of managing multiple comorbidities makes patients with type II diabetes and hypertension particularly susceptible to medication errors. Such mistakes can increase unfavorable outcomes, jeopardize the effectiveness of treatment, and put further burden on healthcare systems.

Methods:

To assess the frequency and severity of drug-related problems (DRPs) and drug-drug interactions (DDIs) in adults with type II diabetes and hypertension, a

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retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted at DHQ Hospital KDA Kohat. Micromedex® was used to classify and grade DDIs, and the Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe (PCNE) classification system was used to analyze the data.

Results:

A total of 300 patients were included, with 281 DRPs identified. Nearly all patients (93.6%) experienced at least one DRP. The most frequent issues were drug choice problems (60.5%), unnecessary drug treatment (23%), adverse drug reactions (6%), and problems not clearly classified (9.6%). According to Micromedex®, interactions were predominantly Major (56.2%), followed by Moderate (41.8%) and Contraindicated (1.8%). In terms of onset, most were unspecified (77.9%), with delayed (16.6%) and rapid (5.3%) interactions occurring less frequently. Clinical significance ratings showed most interactions as Fair (70.4%), with fewer classified as Good (23.5%) or Excellent (5.9%).

Conclusion

Medication errors and drug interactions are highly prevalent in patients with type II diabetes and hypertension. Strengthening prescribing practices and medication monitoring can reduce risks and improve treatment outcomes

Keywords: Type-ii diabetes, Medication errors, Hypertension, Polypharmacy; Drug-Drug Interactions

Introduction

The global burden of type II diabetes has surged in recent decades, with estimates indicating that over 800 million adults are living with diabetes as of 2022, a steep rise from earlier years underscoring the disease's expanding footprint, especially in low- and middle-income countries [1] Concurrently, hypertension affects nearly one in three adults worldwide, with disproportionate prevalence and poorer control in resource-poor settings [2-4]. The co-occurrence of these two chronic conditions is common and clinically important: patients with diabetes often develop hypertension, amplifying their cardiovascular risk profile and complicating therapeutic strategies [5-9]

Managing patients with both conditions frequently involves complex medication regimens, raising the risk of drug-drug interactions and medication errors. These errors may stem from inappropriate drug choice, dosing mistakes, drug duplication, improper duration, or poor administration practices. There is a significantly higher chance of adverse events and less-than-ideal treatment when there are several comorbidities and polypharmacy. Few studies have systematically described the nature and frequency of drug-related problems in patients with both type II diabetes and hypertension in Pakistan, especially in district-level hospitals, despite the known risks. [10-13].

Understanding regional trends in prescription errors is essential in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province, which has limited access to clinical pharmacy services and healthcare resources, including drug-interaction screening. Interventions could be ineffective or misguided in the absence of such data. This study, carried out at DHQ Hospital Kohat, attempts to close that gap by evaluating medication-related issues and drug-drug interactions in patients with type II diabetes and hypertension in the past and investigating the relationships between these errors and clinical and demographic characteristics..

Targeted interventions, like clinical pharmacy integration, prescribing checklists, or

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electronic interaction alerts, can be informed by the most prevalent and clinically significant medication errors in this patient population. This will help to improve therapeutic outcomes and prevent avoidable harm in similar low-resource hospital settings.

Methodology

This six-month retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted at DHQ Hospital Kohat to assess the frequency and seriousness of drug-drug interactions in adult patients with type II diabetes and hypertension. 300 people in all were included, which is more than the 195 minimum sample size that Epi Info, Version 6 (CDC, Atlanta, GA) recommends.

Eligible participants were adults above 35 years of age from both genders who had confirmed diagnoses of type II diabetes with hypertension and complete prescription records. Prescriptions lacking essential details such as patient age or medication information were excluded. Data collection encompassed demographic characteristics (age, gender), clinical parameters (length of hospital stay, laboratory findings), and therapeutic details, including prescribed drugs and co-medications. All prescriptions were systematically reviewed to identify, classify, and assess potential medication errors, with a focus on drug–drug interactions, using the Micromedex® database. Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Kohat University of Science and Technology (KUST) Research Ethical Committee under reference number KUST/Ethical Committee/1633.

3. Results

3.1 Patient Demographics

Out of 300 patients included in the study, 113 (37.6%) were male and 187 (62.3%) were female. The majority of patients (58.0%) were between 50–64 years of age, followed by 17.0% in the 65–79 range, 13.3% between 35–49 years, 10.6% between 80–94 years, and only 1.0% were older than 94.

Table 1. Patient demographic distribution

Characteristics	Categories	n (%)
Gender	Male	113 (37.6)
	Female	187 (62.3)
Age (years)	35–49	40 (13.3)
	50–64	174 (58.0)
	65–79	51 (17.0)
	80–94	32 (10.6)
	>94	3 (1.0)

3.2 Hospital Stay and Prescriptions

The duration of hospitalization varied, with 40.6% staying 3–5 days, 31.3% staying 6–9 days, 22.3% staying 1–2 days, and 5.6% staying longer than 9 days. Polypharmacy was common, as 90.3% of patients received more than five

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medications.

Table 2. Hospital stay and prescribed medicines

Variable	Categories	n (%)
Hospital stay	1–2 days	67 (22.3)
	3–5 days	122 (40.6)
	6–9 days	94 (31.3)
	>9 days	17 (5.6)
No. of drugs	<5 drugs	29 (9.6)
	≥5 drugs	271 (90.3)

3.3 Drug–Drug Interactions

Potential drug–drug interactions (DDIs) were observed in 281 patients (93%), while 19 (7%) had no interactions. The severity analysis showed that more than half (56.2%) were classified as **major**, 41.8% as **moderate**, and 1.8% as **contraindicated**. Most interactions had documentation quality rated as **fair (70.4%)**, with fewer rated as **good (23.5%)** and **excellent (5.9%)**.

Table 3. Profile of drug–drug interactions

Category	Classification	n (%)
DDI presence	Yes	281 (93)
	No	19 (7)
Severity	Contraindicated	6 (1.8)
	Major	179 (56.2)
	Moderate	133 (41.8)
Onset	Rapid	17 (5.3)
	Delayed	53 (16.6)
	Not specified	248 (77.9)
Documentation	Excellent	19 (5.9)
	Good	75 (23.5)
	Fair	224 (70.4)

3.4 Comorbidities

Among 218 patients with additional complications, ischemic heart disease (19.7%), urinary tract infections (16%), and diabetic foot ulcers (14.6%) were the most common. Other conditions included congestive cardiac failure (12.3%), ischemic stroke (7.7%), and chronic kidney disease (6.8%). Less frequent comorbidities included COPD (5%), nephropathy (3.2%), and septic shock (1%).

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Table 4. Comorbid conditions among patients (n=218)

Comorbidity	n (%)	Comorbidity	n (%)
IHD	43 (19.7)	CKD	15 (6.8)
UTI	35 (16.0)	Stroke	17 (7.7)
DFU	32 (14.6)	CCF	27 (12.3)
COPD	11 (5.0)	Nephropathy	7 (3.2)
Osteoporosis	6 (2.7)	Septic Shock	2 (1.0)
CVA	4 (2.0)	Dyslipidemia	1 (0.5)

3.5 Antihypertensive–Antidiabetic Interactions

A total of 509 potential interactions were observed between antihypertensive and antidiabetic drugs. The most frequent interactions involved **furosemide (15.9%)**, **nebivolol (15.7%)**, **valsartan (14.5%)**, and **bisoprolol (13.3%)**. Less frequent interactions were seen with ramipril (5.1%), amlodipine (5.6%), carvedilol (8%), and others below 2%.

3.6 Causes of Drug-Related Problems

Analysis of prescriptions revealed errors in drug selection, dosing, treatment duration, and administration process. Common issues included excessive polypharmacy (10.7%), inappropriate dosing (10.3%), wrong timing of drug administration (9.7%), and therapeutic duplication (7.1%). Other errors involved incorrect drug combinations and unnecessary prescriptions. In total, 279 medication-related issues were identified. The most frequent problems were **suboptimal treatment effect (33%)**, **unnecessary drug treatment (23%)**, and **untreated symptoms (20%)**. Adverse drug events were noted in 6% of cases, while unclear issues accounted for 9.6%.

Table 5. Identified drug-related problems (n=279)

Problem Category	n (%)
Suboptimal effect	93 (33.0)
Untreated symptoms	57 (20.0)
No effect despite use	21 (7.5)
Adverse drug events	17 (6.0)
Unnecessary treatment	65 (23.0)
Unclear issues	27 (9.6)

The findings highlight the critical role of careful monitoring and medication review by clinical pharmacists to minimize drug-related problems. Proper documentation of patient history, cautious selection of medicines with fewer interactions, patient

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counseling, and regular laboratory monitoring are essential strategies to reduce adverse drug outcomes.

5. Discussion

This retrospective study conducted in the Medical A ward of DHQ Hospital Kohat evaluated medication errors and drug–drug interactions among 300 patients with type-II diabetes and hypertension. Female patients predominated (62.3%), and the majority were over 50 years of age, which aligns with earlier evidence that aging and gender differences contribute to hypertension risk. Hypertension prevalence tends to increase with advancing age due to vascular stiffness, impaired endothelial function, and cumulative exposure to cardiovascular risk factors. Moreover, postmenopausal women experience higher susceptibility owing to reduced estrogen levels, which play a protective role in vascular dilation and blood pressure regulation. Lifestyle-related behaviors such as diet, stress, and reduced physical activity further explain the higher prevalence observed in both aging populations and gender-specific groups [14–16].

Polypharmacy was common, as 90.3% of patients received more than five drugs, supporting earlier reports that higher drug counts increase the likelihood of adverse interactions [17, 18]. In this study, 93% of patients experienced at least one drug–drug interaction, demonstrating that medication errors are a significant challenge in this population. Comorbidities such as ischemic heart disease, urinary tract infections, and diabetic foot ulcers were frequent, further complicating treatment [19, 20].

Among antihypertensive–antidiabetic combinations, furosemide and nebivolol showed the highest interaction rates, while atenolol and metoprolol were less involved. Similar to previous findings, clinically significant interactions such as amlodipine with clopidogrel may reduce therapeutic efficacy by inhibiting metabolic activation of clopidogrel. In line with Micromedex assessment, most interactions were classified as major or moderate, with limited high-quality evidence available for many [21, 22].

The findings are consistent with reports that Pakistan’s healthcare system faces gaps in clinical pharmacy services, computerized screening, and drug information resources, particularly in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa [23–25]. Such deficiencies contribute to a higher risk of preventable drug-related problems. Overall, this study emphasizes the need for regular prescription review, close monitoring of laboratory reports, and integration of clinical pharmacy services to minimize the impact of drug–drug interactions and improve therapeutic outcomes.

Conclusion

This study highlights the high prevalence of drug–drug interactions and drug-related problems among patients with type-II diabetes and hypertension at DHQ Hospital Kohat. Most interactions were of major or moderate severity, largely driven by polypharmacy and comorbidities. Strengthening clinical pharmacy services, ensuring closer monitoring of prescriptions, and fostering collaboration between physicians and pharmacists are essential to reduce preventable medication errors and improve patient safety.

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